

Kinetics of Oxidation of α -Amino Acids by Periodate

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Kinetics of oxidation of α -amino acids viz. glycine, alanine, phenylalanine, glutamic acid and aspartic acid by periodate has been studied in aqueous medium with a view to find out the behaviour of the periodate, which is a specific oxidant for 1,2-glycols. The order in [amino acid] and [periodate] were found to be one each and the overall reaction followed second order kinetics. The rates decreased with increase in $[H^+]$. Addition of salts like KCl, $NaNO_3$ and $NaClO_4$ had negligible effect on the rates. The products of oxidation were identified as the corresponding aldehydes apart from CO_2 and NH_3 . A mechanism similar to that observed in the oxidation of 1,2-glycols is proposed to explain the results. Activation parameters are also presented and discussed.

PERIODATE has been used as a selective oxidizing agent for the cleavage of 1,2-glycols¹, α -hydroxy acids², 1,2-diketones³, amino alcohols⁴ and other organic substrates⁵. Clamp *et al*⁶ suggested that oxidation of glycine and N-substituted glycines proceed by an electrophilic attack of the oxidant on nitrogen giving an intermediate complex which decomposes to products via the imino compound. As no detailed kinetic investigation has so far been attempted it was thought worth while to study the kinetics of oxidation of some α -amino acids by periodate to get a clear picture of the mechanism.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of BDH (AR) grade and purified wherever necessary by standard methods. KOH and HOAc solutions in different proportions were used for the variation of pH . KCl was used for adjusting the ionic strength. The rate of the reaction was followed iodometrically⁷ and the concentration of periodate at any time was calculated by making allowance for the reduction of IO_3^- . The products of oxidation were CO_2 , NH_3 and the corresponding aldehydes and these were detected by their characteristic tests⁸.

Results and Discussion

The reaction followed second order kinetics (Table-1) with first order dependence on each of the reactants. The rate of oxidation increased with increase in pH (Table-2) for all amino acids except in the case of glutamic and aspartic acids where a rate maxima was observed at pH 4.5 and 7 respectively. This may be due to the existence of different periodate species formed probably by the dissociation of the main species viz $H_5IO_6^{9a,b}$. According to the equilibrium proposed by Crouthamel and coworkers⁹

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON THE [AMINO ACID] AND $[KIO_4]$

$\mu = 0.008 M$; $pH = 6.5$; Temperature = 324 K

Glycine mol.lit ⁻¹	$[KIO_4] \times 10^3$ mol. lit ⁻¹	$k' \times 10^8$ min ⁻¹	$k'/[A.A] \times 10^8$ lit mol. ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
0.100	0.400	2.95	—
0.100	0.800	3.05	30.5
0.200	0.800	6.56	32.8
0.300	0.800	9.20	30.7
0.400	0.800	13.8	34.6
0.500	0.800	17.3	34.6
0.600	0.800	21.2	35.3
0.750	0.800	26.2	34.9

if $H_4IO_6^-$ were to be the reactive species, increase in $[H^+]$ should decrease the rate. Such a trend was observed (Table-2) in the present work suggesting H_5IO_6 to be the reactive species. From the oxidation studies of glycols¹⁰ Buist and Bunton suggested that a uninegatively charged complex in its dehydrated form splits readily into products and that the undissociated (H_5IO_6) or dinegatively charged ($H_3IO_6^{2-}$) complexes are inert. The effect of added salts viz. KCl, $NaNO_3$ and $NaClO_4$ (0.050—0.450M) was found to be negligible indicating the reaction to be an ion-dipole type one. The intermediate complex suggested by earlier workers in the oxidation of other organic substrates could not be detected kinetically in the present work as the plot of $1/k'$ vs $1/[A.A]$ was linear (fig-1) with no intercept. A mechanism involving the formation of an unstable intermediate in a slow rate determining step by the electrophilic attack on nitrogen

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF RATE WITH pH

		[KIO ₃]=0.005 M ;									
		Temperature=323 K.									
pH		10.2	9.60	9.00	8.60	7.10	6.20	5.10	4.50	4.20	3.00
k' × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	gly.	—	6.68	3.45	2.30	—	0.500	0.380	—	0.320	0.265
	glu.	1.57	—	1.62	1.68	1.72	—	1.89	2.07	1.96	1.54
	asp.	2.60	—	4.20	4.61	5.61	—	4.25	3.68	3.40	2.15

gly.=glycine=0.200 M ; glu.=glutamic acid=0.040M ;
asp.=aspartic acid=0.040M.

by periodate is proposed to explain the oxidation. This intermediate cyclizes and undergoes C-C bond fission giving rise to products via the imino compound (Chart-1).

The observed rate law may be written as follows :

$$\frac{-d[P]_t}{dt} = k''[P]_t [A.A] \quad \dots (2)$$

where [P]_t = Concentration of total periodate species

$$= [H_6IO_6] + [H_4IO_6^- + IO_4^-] + [H_3IO_6^{2-}] + [H_2IO_6^{3-}]$$

and [A.A.] = Concentration of amino acid.

It has been shown by earlier workers³ that in the pH range 4–10 the most likely reactive species are H₄IO₆⁻, IO₄⁻ and H₃IO₆²⁻. Therefore the rate expression for the reaction in this pH range may be written as

$$-\frac{d[P]_t}{dt} = \{k_1[H_4IO_6^- + IO_4^-] + k_2[H_3IO_6^{2-}]\} [A.A.] \dots (3)$$

where k₁ and k₂ are the rate coefficients for the reaction of mononegatively and dinegatively charged species with A.A. respectively.

Equating (2) and (3)

$$k''[P]_t [A.A] = \{k_1[H_4IO_6^- + IO_4^-] + k_2[H_3IO_6^{2-}]\} [A.A] \quad \dots (4)$$

$$\text{or } k'' = k_1/x_1 + k_2/x_2 \quad \dots (5)$$

where x₁ and x₂ are the correction terms for the availability of the periodate species and can be expressed as follows :

$$x_1 = 1 + \frac{\bar{K}_2 \cdot f^-}{f^{2-} \cdot a_H^+}$$

$$x_2 = 1 + \frac{f^{2-} \cdot a_H^+}{K_2 \cdot f^-}$$

where \bar{K}_2 = apparent second ionisation constant of periodate species^{1,1} and can be expressed as

$$K_2 = \frac{[H_3IO_6^{2-}] f^{2-} \cdot a_H^+}{[H_4IO_6^- + IO_4^-] f^-}$$

where,

a_H⁺ is hydrogen ion activity obtained from pH measurements.

f⁻ and f²⁻ are activity coefficients of mono and dianion of periodate species (calculated from Davies' equation^{1,2}).

The values of k₁ and k₂ for glycine calculated from the experimental k'' values are as follows :

$$k_1 = (1.25 \times 10^{-4} \text{ to } 1.38 \times 10^{-4}) \text{ lit. mol}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1} \text{ and } k_2 = (1.29 \times 10^{-3} \text{ to } 0.93 \times 10^{-3}) \text{ lit. mol}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}.$$

The marked increase in the rate of oxidation above pH 7 in the case of glycine, alanine and phenylalanine could be explained by assuming the cyclization of the monoester to be base catalysed similar to the observations made by Buist and Bunton in the pinacol oxidation¹³. The hydroxyl ion acting as a powerful catalyst compared to water in the basic medium, releases the proton of the hydroxyl group thereby favouring cyclization (Chart-2).¹

Where B = base (OH⁻)

Chart 2

In the case of glutamic and aspartic acids a rate maximum appears at pH 4.5 and 7, respectively. The rate maxima at these pH values are to be expected because periodate monoanions exist predominantly⁹ only in the pH range 3-7. It is likely that the base catalysis is suppressed in the case of more acidic amino acids due to the presence of additional carboxylic acid groups present in the molecule. The rate maximum at higher pH for aspartic acid may be due to its lower pK_1 and pK_2 values compared to glutamic acid.

The order of the rates of oxidation is phenylalanine > aspartic acid > glutamic acid > glycine > alanine. Thus it is clear that the rates of oxidation increase as the pK_a values decrease or the dissociation of the amino acids increases (Table-3). Activation

TABLE 3—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS AT 338 K

Amino acid	pK_a of the A.A.	$k'' \times 10^8$ lit mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	ΔE^\ddagger k cal mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger k cal mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger k cal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ e u.
glycine	2.34	2.50	19.1	18.4	23.9	16.3
alanine	2.34	1.80	18.8	18.1	24.1	17.8
phenylalanine	1.83	11.9	21.5	20.8	22.9	6.00
aspartic acid	1.88	3.40	13.1	12.4	23.7	33.4
glutamic acid	2.19	2.70	16.2	15.5	23.9	24.6

parameters have been calculated and are listed in the Table 3. The high ΔS^\ddagger value in case of phenylalanine is indicative of a less rigid activated complex. A plot of ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger was linear (Fig. 1) indicating that

Fig. 1. (A) $1/k' \times 10^8$ vs $1/[A.A.]$

Temp. = 324 K; $\mu = 0.008$ M; pH = 6.5
(B) ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger

this reaction series follows isokinetic phenomena¹⁴. The isokinetic temperature (β) was found to be 300°K which is decidedly lower than the experimental temperature range (323-338°K) used suggesting that the reactions are entropy controlled.

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